

Enabling Next-Generation Smart Homes through Bert Personalized Food Recommendations - RecipeBERT

1st Divya Mereddy

computer science
Vanderbilt University
Nashville, TN

divya.mereddy@vanderbilt.edu

2nd Jeevan Beedareddy

Houzz
Nashville, TN
beedareddy@gmail.com

Abstract—This paper introduces RecipeBERT, a BERT-based NLP model for personalized meal recommendations in the context of smart homes research. As a content-based recommendation system, it ranks recipes based on semantic similarity of ingredients and procedures. Recipes have similar ingredients and procedures are considered similar recipes. The proposed model effectively curates a personalized list of top recipes, taking into account the household’s eating patterns over an extended period. Unlike previous BERT-based models, which lacked comprehensive fine-tuning to adopt to food recommendation domain, our approach enhances efficiency through fine-tuning BERT to better deliver tailored recommendations. Our evaluation included testing different transformer models: Sentence BERT and its distilled version along with Sentence-distilled RoBERTa, which we optimized through both full and various partial fine-tuning methods. This comparative analysis helped us determine the most suitable model and fine-tuning process for accurately adapting BERT model to this task. Here we hypothesize that carefully fine-tuned LLM’s can demonstrate improved performance in the recipe recommendation domain compared to pretrained models. In this work, we utilized a semi-automated labeling method combining distillation and manual data review process for fine-tuning data needs. The complete code and dataset for our project are available at <https://github.com/DivyaMereddy007/RecipeBert/tree/main/RecipeBert>.

Index Terms—Personalized food recommendations, BERT, SBERT, RecipeBERT

I. INTRODUCTION

While artificial intelligence continues to revolutionize various industries, the smart home industry has not reached the next-generation level yet. For a home to be truly smart, it should fully predict the needs of its residents, responding with appropriate services promptly. Imagine living in a home that not only manages itself but also enhances the daily lives of its residents by offering everyday meals food recommendations based on their taste, culture, weather, diet, their interest in trying new recipes. This vision of providing personalized daily meal recommendations drove our research. Our proposed system is to build a BERT-based natural language processing model that predicts recipe similarity. Food has undergone significant evolution throughout history. From the early days of simple fruits and raw meat, humans began appreciating the

complexities of cooked food, exploring different methods and ingredient combinations. While some foods can be consumed raw, many require preparation for safety, texture, and flavor in order to aim to enhance taste, aesthetic appeal, preservation. It may involve various techniques such as cutting, heating, fermentation, and combining with other ingredients. And these heavily influence the taste of a dish. Different people appreciate different recipes based on the taste of dish. People’s interest towards particular ingredient or cooking technique can make them like particular food. Culture, personal taste preferences, dietary habits, and living conditions, including the geographic location of a country, significantly influence people’s food choices[5], [8]. The domain of Food recommendations is very diverse[4].

While several approaches exist to tackle food recommendation problems, such as co-occurrence matrices[33] and FP-growth[25], we have chosen to adopt an NLP-based item similarity model. This decision is driven by the preliminary stage of data collection in our smart home systems, resulting in limited user-to-user data. Leveraging an open-source recipe dataset RecipeNLG, our RecipeBERT model has demonstrated promising results in generating relevant food recommendations. In addition, even in a well matured data environment, content based recommendation models can be great solution for cold start problems. This research aims to explore the potential of personalized content based food recommendations in the context of smart homes, taking into account individual preferences and available data sources. While the industry has some work on recipe recommendations[28], [18], [13], [31], [24], [12], [20], [15], [21], carefully fine-tuned NLP Bert based recipe recommendation models do not exist. we aim to fill that gap.

In our work, We have enhanced the efficiency of pretrained Bert model based Recipe Recommendation system by fine tuning the BERT model to more effectively deliver personalized meal recommendations. Our RecipeBERT evaluation included testing two different transformer models: BERT[7] and RoBERTa[19], which we optimized through both full and various partial finetuning methods[11], [17], [9], [6], [30]. For

model fine-tuning, we utilized a dataset annotated based on semi-automatic labeling methods, which is based on combination of manual correlations provided by humans and data generated through a ChatGPT-based distillation process[16]. Overall, our fully fine-tuned RecipeBERT model achieved improved performance compared to recent state-of-the-art content based similarity (recipe recommendation use case) models [20], [15].

Just as people rely on recommendations for movies or entertainment[10], recommendation systems are poised to transform the realm of food recommendations. These systems are about to start new era by transitioning the paradigm from human-generated food advice to AI-curated guidance[1].

Rationale for NLP Application in Recipe Recommendations: Traditional recommendation systems, such as user-to-user correlations or co-occurrence matrices, typically rely on extensive user interaction data. For startups, such data may be sparse due to a smaller user base. Additionally, industry-wide, there is a notable scarcity of datasets that facilitate item-to-item recipe similarity predictions. Conversely, recipe data is abundant and amenable to augmentation. Utilizing Natural Language Processing (NLP) for recipe recommendation enables more flexible and dynamic inference, even with limited initial data. As the product evolves, users can effortlessly contribute new recipes, thereby enriching the dataset. For instance, upon discovering the delights of French cuisine, one may simply incorporate a comprehensive French recipe dataset or selectively add favored recipes to the system. This approach significantly simplifies data enhancement and keeps the recommendation engine current and personalized.

In summary, the key contributions of this paper are as follows:

Model Development and Comparison: By through experimenting and comparing different models, we present a fine-tuned Sentence-BERT model for predicting recipe similarity, tailored for the culinary domain. In addition, we introduce a smaller, distilled version of the model optimized for resource efficiency.

Semi-Automated Labeling Approach: To satisfy the data labeling needs, we also introduced a novel semi-automated labeling method that combines manual annotations with ChatGPT chain of thoughts-based automatic data labels creation.

II. RELATED WORK

NLP-based (semantic)content similarity prediction systems have gained significant popularity in recent times[14], [26]. Utilizing these techniques, food recommendation systems that leverages food profiling, user profiling, and user feedback to provide personalized suggestions [3] have developed. Additionally, notable research efforts have emerged in the domain of healthy food recommendations contributing to advancements in this area[29], [32].

Similarly, traditional DL based recommendations were also explored using NLP techniques[18]. Graph-based recommendation systems has also became popular these days[28]. Overall, these models are either based on non machine learning

or traditional deep learning models or created for slightly different use cases.

In this research paper, we are working on another approach to food recommendation, which differs from the above paper methods due to its reliance on LLM's and use case of personalized recipe recommendation. It's based on Bert model. Our research contribution is specially curating a fine-tuned LLM-based recipe recommendation model.

A. LLM's in Recommendation Systems:

On the technology side, significant research is being conducted on using BERT and large language models (LLMs) for content-based similarity predictions in NLP domain. Recent research has explored different Bert model fine-tuning techniques to adapt pre-trained models on domain-specific data with an aim to improve performance on textual similarity tasks in areas like e-commerce, social media, and biomedicine and more. These techniques include Lora[11], [17], [9], a few layers training[6], and distillation-based methods[30] etc. In our paper, we aim to implement these techniques in the food recommendations domain and create RecipeBERT by carefully comparing different LLM's and fine-tuning techniques.

B. LLM Embedding-Based Approaches in the Culinary Domain:

Using similar LLM embedding-based approaches, several groups have developed applications such as CookingQA [14], new recipe prediction[26], [21], and more similar applications. Additionally, there has been research on recommendation systems, including recipe recommendations, using prompt-based data augmentation [20], [15], [21] with frozen LLMs or deep learning models. While there has also been considerable work on recipe recommendation models using BERT[13], [31], [24], [12], no one has performed an extensive fine-tuning of these models and compared them with other LLMs. In this paper, we aim to fill that gap by creating a finely curated RecipeBERT model for food recommendations. In addition, we have explored the efficacy of constructive learning-based distillation models [27] for text-based recommendation systems in the recipe domain.

III. RECIPEBERT

Our research paper focuses on developing a food recommendation model that leverages text and NLP-based similarity systems. The effectiveness of a recipe and its taste are influenced by various factors, with the choice and sequence of ingredients added to dish playing a crucial role. NLP models, particularly Bert, excel in capturing the similarity of words and sentences, allowing us to effectively analyze the importance of food ingredients (via word similarity) and their sequencing (via sentence similarity calculations). For instance, someone who enjoys raw tomatoes may prefer dishes like salsa and tomato soup. Similarly, an individual fond of Indian cuisine with specific flavors and ingredients might enjoy related dishes from other cuisines, such as Panda Express Black Pepper Chicken. The similarity in ingredients and cooking methods

significantly influences the likelihood of a recipe being favored by a user. This approach mirrors the natural human process of recommending recipes based on known preferences for ingredients and culinary methods. The model also considers factors such as potential dietary restrictions, which play essential roles in food preferences. While the model does not explicitly consider dietary restrictions, it subconsciously incorporates these factors through the analysis of ingredient similarities and cooking methods.

A. Background

1) *Sentence-Transformers*: While the BERT model can directly assess sentence similarity by concatenating two sentences with a [SEP] token and processing them, this method becomes computationally prohibitive with large datasets. For instance, analyzing a corpus of 10,000 sentences would require about 50 million sentence pair evaluations, exceeding 60 hours of computation on standard GPU setups. The computation time significantly increases for semantic search tasks, reaching 40 seconds per query, which is impractical for real-time applications[23].

Sentence-BERT (SBERT)[23] addresses these inefficiencies by modifying the pre-trained BERT model to generate sentence embeddings optimized for quick and effective comparison using cosine similarity. SBERT employs a siamese and triplet network structure during training. This setup processes pairs of sentences through two BERT networks with shared weights, ensuring each sentence is embedded similarly. SBERT’s training integrates a triplet loss function, which enhances the model’s ability to distinguish between semantically similar and dissimilar sentences, and it is fine-tuned on Natural Language Inference (NLI) datasets like SNLI and MultiNLI. These datasets provide sentence pairs with labels of entailment, contradiction, or neutrality, enabling SBERT to learn nuanced semantic relationships efficiently.

Algorithm 1 Main SudoCode: Finding Similar Recipes for a Given Recipe in Sorted Order

Require: sentences, recipe_ids, top_k
Ensure: similarities_sorted

- 1: sentence_vectors \leftarrow GET_SENTENCE_EMBEDDINGS (sentences)
- 2: cs \leftarrow CALCULATE_COSINE_SIMILARITY (sentence_vectors)
- 3: **for** each similarity set in cs **do**
- 4: similarities_sorted \leftarrow RETURN_SIMILAR_ITEMS(cs, recipe_ids, top_k)
- 5: **end for**
- 6: **return** similarities_sorted

2) *Item To Item Similarity System Development*: Along with Bert LLM(Sentence Transformer), by utilizing cosine similarity as the machine learning head we can find similarities between the embeddings of the recipes which represents semantic similarity. As mentioned before this methodology

is a NLP-based item-to-item content based similarity problem. Algorithm 1 explains how the operation can be performed on a $n \times n$ matrix where recipe data contains n recipes. Here we compute similarity between every recipe vs every other recipe in the dataset.

B. Proposed Method:

While the above simple methods can help us develop a recipe recommendation system, we argue that fine-tuned pre-trained LLM-based systems can demonstrate better results. To explore this hypothesis, we evaluated two different transformer models: Sentence BERT and Sentence distilled RoBERTa, and explored both full and partial fine-tuning techniques. These models are chosen because of their capabilities in capturing semantic similarities between text sequences [23], [19]. RoBERTa (Robustly Optimized BERT Approach)[19], builds upon the original BERT architecture. It is trained for longer periods with larger mini-batches and more data, which helps it learn finer language patterns and nuances. RoBERTa omits the Next Sentence Prediction (NSP) objective, which has been proved to be less beneficial for downstream tasks such as classification[19]. We also hypothesis that RoBERTa due to its training optimizations and the omission of NSP objective, can also enhance a type of performance in the recipe recommendation task such as food recommendations.

We also aim to investigate whether distilled models, such as Sentence Distilled RoBERTa, can perform equally well for our task, given their strong performance compared to their teacher models, such as BERT and other encoder models. Considering the generic nature of recipe recommendations, we hypothesize that even smaller architectures could achieve good accuracy.

C. Semi-Automatic Annotation

In this work, we employed a semi-automated approach for labeling recipe similarity by leveraging both manual annotations and the capabilities of ChatGPT chain of thoughts for automated labeling. Initially, two human labelers, trained specifically in the culinary domain, manually annotated 2,500 recipe pairs. Recipe similarity was determined based on overlap in ingredients and cooking processes, with similarity values assigned on a continuous scale from 0.00 to 0.10, reflecting nuanced variations between recipes. The manual annotations achieved a high inter-annotator correlation of 0.91, indicating substantial agreement between the labelers. Following this, we utilized ChatGPT chain-of-thought process to semi-automate the labeling of additional data. The prompts were designed to guide the model in determining similarity based on the same criteria of ingredient and cooking process overlap, ensuring consistency with the manual annotation strategy. ChatGPT was instructed to generate similarity scores with two-decimal precision. To validate the performance of the semi-automated annotations, we compared the ChatGPT-generated labels against the manually annotated dataset, resulting in a strong correlation of 0.85 between the two sets of labels. This indicates that the semi-automated process closely approximates human

judgment, allowing for scalable annotation while maintaining a high level of accuracy.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Experiment Setup

1) *datasets* : We utilized widely known RecipeNLG dataset for our recipes text and ingredient text data. The RecipeNLG dataset provides a comprehensive collection of cooking recipes, offering rich and diverse information for our research purposes. The dataset includes detailed descriptions of ingredients, cooking procedures, and other relevant metadata associated with each recipe. For fine-tuning and model validation we have created gold-standard correlation data for a sub set(12.5k records) of RecipeNLG data using ChatGPT chain of thoughts method based correlation creation with additional manual data review. Here we took ChatGPT distillation process[16] as reference and further enhanced the quality of the data with manual review process.

2) *Evaluation Methods*: In our model validation, we utilized different metrics specially different correlation measure to validate our models. Correlation, in broad terms, measures how strongly two variables are related. There are several types of correlation coefficients, including:

- Pearson’s Correlation (R): measures linear relationship between two variables. Suitable when data is continuous.
- Spearman’s Rank Correlation (Rho): Spearman’s correlation is similar to Pearson’s correlation calculated on ordinal data. Since data for Spearman’s correlation is ordinal, the data distribution need not be normal. To calculate the correlation we will be looking at difference in rankings for each pair (i.e. rankings of variable 1 and variable 2 for each value).
- Kendall’s Tau : Kendall’s Tau is another method to measure similarity between two rankings. This looks at the number of concordant and discordant pairs. Kendall’s Tau works better if there are no ties in rankings.
- Goodman - Kruskal’s Gamma: This is similar to Kendall’s Tau and handles ties in rankings and outliers.

In our work, we specifically utilized ranking metrics such as Spearman’s Rank Correlation, Kendall’s Tau, and Goodman-Kruskal’s Gamma, as they better represent the ranking of recommended items compared to Pearson’s correlation, which is less relevant in the context of our recommendation domain. Pearson’s correlation is less relevant because it measures linear relationships between continuous variables, while recommendation tasks typically involve ordinal data and require evaluating the order of ranked items rather than their linear relationship. As this synthesized dataset size is relatively small (12K records), we followed n fold cross validation to make sure we capture the generalized results using small dataset. Here we took n as 3.

V. MAIN RESULTS

A. Comparative Analysis of SBERT and TF-IDF

In our work we consider the TF-IDF model as the base model as we at least want to perform better than the TF-IDF

model in the worst case. In our comparative study, the basic TF-IDF model showed a Spearman correlation of 0.39 on test dataset, indicating moderate performance. On the other hand, the BERT-based model demonstrated enhanced effectiveness with an Spearman correlation score of 0.64. A notable number of the BERT model’s similarity scores were in the upper range, between 0.6 and 1.0. In contrast, the TF-IDF model’s scores were often found in the lower range, from 0.0 to 0.4. But rank-based metrics like spearman’s Rho reported was able to standard these similarities by using rank-based methods.

B. Comparative Analysis of Pretrained SBERT and Pretrained Sentence Distilled RoBERTa

In this study, we investigated the efficacy of two pre-trained transformer-based models, SBERT (Sentence-BERT) and a Sentence Distilled RoBERTa-based model, in determining semantic similarities between culinary recipes.

SBERT Evaluation Results: The SBERT model demonstrated a moderate positive correlation in both Spearman’s (0.6448396), Goodman Kruskal Gamma (0.6053891), and Kendall’s coefficient of 0.5 metrics. These results underscore SBERT’s proficiency in generating semantically meaningful embeddings for sentences or short paragraphs, which is intrinsic to its architecture. Given SBERT’s optimization for sentence-level processing, its performance in this context is indicative of its potential for applications requiring nuanced semantic understanding, particularly in domains like culinary analysis where the semantic integrity of recipe descriptions is paramount.

RoBERTa-based Model Evaluation: Conversely, the Sentence Distilled RoBERTa-based approach exhibited significantly lower correlation coefficients, with Spearman at 0.121, Goodman Kruskal Gamma metrics at 0.111, and Kendall’s coefficient of 0.094. This disparity suggests a limitation in the RoBERTa-based model’s ability to accurately reflect the semantic nuances of culinary recipes. Although RoBERTa is robustly optimized, its general-purpose pretraining objectives may not be as effective for tasks that require fine-grained sentence-level embeddings. Sentence Distilled RoBERTa, while distilled for efficiency, might not retain the same level of optimization for sentence similarity tasks as SBERT. SBERT is specifically optimized for sentence-level tasks using a siamese and triplet network structure, whereas RoBERTa, including its distilled version, is not.

C. Fine-Tuning Impact on SBERT for Recipe Similarity Analysis(Full Model Fine Tuning)

Fine-tuning Sentence Transformer models for tasks like recipe similarity can be approached in four ways[23]: sentence pairs with similarity labels; similar sentence pairs like paraphrases; single sentences with integer labels to form triplets for classification-oriented fine-tuning; and triplets focusing on relational dynamics without explicit labels.

For our recipe similarity project, Case 1 is the most fitting, as it aligns with datasets that contain paired sentences (e.g., recipe descriptions) with similarity scores. The fine-tuning process under this case uses a loss function that aligns

the sentences in vector space according to their similarity scores—closely scored sentences are drawn nearer, while those with dissimilar labels are pushed apart. The choice of loss function hinges on the label type and CosineSimilarityLoss work best for floating-point labels.

Given that the similarity scores in the project are floating-point numbers, the CosineSimilarityLoss function is ideal. This choice is further supported by the nature of the validation and training data, which consist of recipe pairs (recipe1, recipe2) alongside a similarity score, thus fitting the structure needed for Case 1’s fine-tuning approach. This structured pairing and labeling of the dataset facilitate the effective optimization of the model for the nuanced task of assessing recipe similarity.

What happens in fine-tuning:

As per[22], the paper analyzes “what happens to BERT embeddings during fine-tuning on downstream NLP tasks”, they find that linguistic features like syntax are not forgotten during fine-tuning, but tasks can differ in how they surface or obscure different phenomena. Fine-tuning tends to only affect the top few layers of BERT, with some variation across tasks. SQuAD(question answering) and MNL(natural language inference) involve relatively shallow changes, while dependency parsing induces deeper changes. Fine-tuning has a large effect on in-domain examples but a weaker effect on out-of-domain sentences, which remain closer to the original pre-trained embeddings. Overall, fine-tuning conservatively modifies BERT, preserving linguistic features, changing only a fraction of layers, and being specific to the fine-tuning domain. This suggests room for improvement in generalization and transferability.

In the context of this study, the full fine-tuned SBERT’s performance, with Spearman’s Rank Correlation Coefficient of 0.7431190 and Goodman Kruskal Gamma correlation of 0.7431190, illustrates its enhanced ability to discern and quantify the semantic similarities within the culinary domain. This represents a significant 18% of Goodman Kruskal Gamma correlation improvement and 13% improvement spearman correlation over the pre-trained SBERT. The fine-tuning process has evidently allowed SBERT to adjust its sentence embeddings to better align with the specific characteristics and requirements of the recipe similarity assessment task, leading to more accurate and domain-specific performance. Performance comparisons are clearly shown in figure 1. Through out the experiments, as the amount of data increased clearly, fine-tuned model performance also increased. Overall best results are observed at epoch 50. Other hyper parameters fine-tuning didnt reported any performance improvement in our optuna hyper parameters search[2].

D. Partially Fine-tuned Sentence-Bert:

Inspired by the promising results of full fine-tuning, we sought to determine if partial fine-tuning could yield even better outcomes. Particularly, we were drawn to partial fine-tuning given that the cooking process—central to our applica-

Fig. 1. Different Models Performance Comparison

tion—aligns closely with general natural language understanding and involves typical command sentences. We investigated two scenarios: fine-tuning only the last two encoder layers of SentenceBERT while keeping other layers frozen, and adding a single non-linear layer to the frozen SentenceBERT for additional fine-tuning.

while both Last Layers Unfreeze Fine-tuning and Frozen BERT with Additional Non-linear Layer Fine-tuning cases performed superior compared to TF-IDF and pre-trained BERT only models, it under performed than the full fine-tuned BERT model by 5% and 2% respectively. For Last Layers Unfreeze Fine-tuning case, the best results were observed at Epoch 25 with a batch size of 32. For Frozen BERT with Additional Non-linear Layer Fine-tuning case, Optimal results were achieved at Epoch 100 with a batch size of 32. Here our additional trained layer is a nonlinear layer with Relu activation with layer normalization and dropout(to avoid over fitting).

In both cases, as the number of epochs increased, the model’s performance initially improved. However, this trend was not sustained and began to reverse, likely due to over fitting.

E. Sentence Bert Model Vs Distilled Sentence Bert Models Performance

Both distilled and non-distilled models benefit substantially from full fine-tuning. This process enables the models to adapt to the specific nuances and requirements of the recipe

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF MODEL PERFORMANCE USING CORRELATION METRICS

Model	Correlation Methods			
	Goodman Kruskal Gamma	Kendall	Spearman	
TF-IDF	0.447	0.326	0.389	
SBERT	0.605	0.502	0.645	
Full Fine Tuned SBERT (40 epochs)	0.759	0.624	0.749	
SBERT Single Layers Partial Fine-tuned SBERT (25 epochs)	0.707	0.589	0.709	
SBERT Two Layers Partial Fine-tuned SBERT (25 epochs)	0.682	0.552	0.681	
SBERT Add New Layer Partial Fine-tuned SBERT (100 epochs)	0.692	0.559	0.680	
Full Fine Tuned Sentence Distilled RoBERTa (50 epochs)	0.751	0.621	0.746	
Full Fine Tuned Sentence Distilled BERT (50 epochs)	0.753	0.622	0.737	

recommendation task, resulting in significant performance improvements. While full fine-tuned sentence BERT achieved 0.759 Goodman kruskal gamma, 0.624 Kendall Correlation and 0.749 Correlation, both distilled models that we explore; Sentence Distilled Bert and Sentence distilled RoBERTa models showed just 1 % less performance. The close performance metrics between the models highlight the effectiveness of the fine-tuning process in bridging the gap between distilled and non-distilled models. Notably, despite distilled models not being pre-trained on contrastive losses, they achieve competitive performance with their non-distilled counterparts after just a few epochs of fine-tuning in specific sub task like culinary similarity prediction. This is particularly impressive given that the non-distilled models were pre-trained on tasks involving sentence comparisons. The BERT model, known for its strong word-level understanding, further refines its ability to capture sentence-level semantics during fine-tuning. This dual capability is particularly beneficial for recipe text data, which includes not only the procedure but also the ingredients list and their combinations. The ability to understand the relationships and combinations of ingredients is crucial for recipe recommendations. On the other hand, Sentence-BERT, specifically optimized for sentence-level tasks, might have experienced issues to understand intricate ingredient combinations while focusing on understanding entire sentences. However, through fine-tuning, Sentence Distilled BERT models manage to adapt and perform well in tasks requiring detailed semantic analysis of both ingredients and procedural steps. The approximately equal performance metrics indicate that distilled models are a highly efficient and effective choice for semantic similarity tasks in NLP. This finding supports the use of distilled models in recipe recommendation applications where computational efficiency is paramount, such as in mobile applications, without significantly sacrificing accuracy.

F. Granular Model Validation on Individual Recipes

To validate the robustness of the fine-tuned model, we evaluated the models performance at individual recipe level. Since score scales are different across various methods, for each recipe in the "Recipe 1" column, we assigned ranks to "Recipe 2" based on predicted similarity. As Gold Standard data similarity scores have a precision of 1 decimal point, there are chances of having the same ranks for multiple recipes.

	Recipe 1	Recipe 2	GS Rank	TFIDF Rank	BERT Rank	Fine Tuned BERT Rank
Contains Fruits	Fresh Strawberry Pie	Fresh Strawberry Pie	1	1	1	1
	Fresh Strawberry Pie	Strawberry Whatever	2	2	11	2
	Fresh Strawberry Pie	Double Cherry Delight	3	19	17	4
	Fresh Strawberry Pie	Broccoli Salad	7	21	25	14
Doesn't contain Fruits	Fresh Strawberry Pie	Buckeye Candy	7	22	18	20
	Fresh Strawberry Pie	Cheeseburger Potato Soup	7	24	32	37
	Quick Barbecue Wings	Quick Barbecue Wings	1	1	1	1
	Quick Barbecue Wings	Chicken Funny	2	2	4	2
Contains Meat	Quick Barbecue Wings	Jewell Ball's Chicken	2	10	3	3
	Quick Barbecue Wings	Pear-Lime Salad	21	20	36	22
	Quick Barbecue Wings	Punch Bowl Fruit Salad	21	20	41	30
	Quick Barbecue Wings	Quick Peppermint Puffs	21	20	27	33
Doesn't contain Meat	Vegetable-Burger Soup	Vegetable-Burger Soup	1	1	1	1
	Vegetable-Burger Soup	Cheeseburger Potato Soup	2	11	4	2
	Vegetable-Burger Soup	Chicken Stew	3	15	15	3
	Vegetable-Burger Soup	Rhubarb Coffee Cake	26	34	34	37
Liquid texture	Vegetable-Burger Soup	Strawberry Whatever	26	12	30	33
	Vegetable-Burger Soup	Watermelon Rind Pickles	26	32	36	34
Solid texture						

Fig. 2. Ranking of various recipes in testing data

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF CORRELATION METHODS FOR RECIPE RANKING

Recipe 1	TF IDF	BERT	Fine-Tuned BERT
Fresh Strawberry Pie	0.343	0.632	0.991
Quick Barbecue Wings	0.579	0.762	0.879
Vegetable-Burger Soup	0.578	0.876	0.889

For each recipe in "Recipe 1", We calculated Goodman Kruskal Gamma correlation between Gold Standard rankings and rankings from various models.

Figure 2 shows is the ranking of various recipes in 'Recipe 2' for two examples recipes of 'Recipe 1'. After calculating correlation for each recipe in "Recipe 1", we took median of the same to understand the correlation at an overall level. Table2 shows the median correlation of all recipes in "Recipe 1" vs all other recipes in the dataset. Undoubtedly the fine-tuned Sentence-BERT model has reported high correlation among other models in all most all cases.

G. Final Conclusions

In this study, we aimed to develop a BERT-based NLP model designed for personalized meal recommendations for

smart homes. Our research aimed to enhance the performance of recommendation systems by leveraging advanced natural language processing techniques, particularly focusing on fine-tuning BERT for the specific domain of food recommendations. We began by outlining the necessity of personalized recommendations in smart homes and the unique challenges posed by the domain of food preferences, which are influenced by cultural, dietary, and individual taste factors. Our approach diverged from traditional recommendation systems that rely heavily on extensive user interaction data, opting instead for an NLP-based model that utilizes the semantic similarity of recipes. The experimental setup involved a comprehensive evaluation of different transformer models, including Sentence-BERT (SBERT) and its distilled version in addition with Sentence-distilled RoBERTa, using various fine-tuning techniques. Our fine-tuning process was meticulously designed to optimize the model for the specific task of recipe recommendation, employing a hybrid dataset that combined data generated through a ChatGPT-based distillation process and additional manual review.

Our findings indicated that the fully fine-tuned SBERT model significantly outperformed traditional TF-IDF models and pre-trained BERT models, achieving a Spearman correlation of 0.743 and a Goodman Kruskal Gamma correlation of 0.759. These results demonstrate the effectiveness of full fine-tuning in capturing the nuanced semantic relationships between recipes, thus providing more accurate and personalized recommendations. Furthermore, the comparative analysis revealed that while partially fine-tuned models performance is slightly less the full fine-tuned SBERT, Sentence-distilled BERT and Sentence distilled RoBERTa models despite its initial underperformance showed competitive results after fine-tuning. This suggests that sentence distilled models, despite their smaller size and computational efficiency, can achieve performance levels similar to their non-distilled counterparts when appropriately fine-tuned in food recommendation domain. These distilled models can be best fit for mobile applications.

Without implementation, along with highlighting the along with highlighting the potential of RecipeBERT to transform the realm of food recommendations in smart homes, we also highlighted the ways researchers can develop small student model using large language models like ChatGPT, especially in cases where the organization doesnt have large amounts of data. By enhancing the accuracy and personalization of meal recommendations, our model can contribute to healthier eating habits and improved user satisfaction.

However, we also acknowledged the limitations of our study, particularly not testing on real time user data. While our results are promising, further research is needed to validate the model in real-time user environment for continuous improvement.

In conclusion, RecipeBERT represents a significant step forward in the application of NLP to personalized food recommendations. Our work demonstrates that compared to existing pretrained bert based context similarity models, fine-tuning bert models can yield substantial performance improve-

ments. The integration of AI-driven meal recommendations holds great promise for enhancing daily life in smart homes, paving the way for more intuitive and responsive smart home environments.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank the OELE Lab and Vanderbilt University for their support and guidance in this project.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ali Ahmadi. The ai food revolution: Reshaping food sciences through artificial intelligence. *International Journal of BioLife Sciences (IJLS)*, 2(1):62–71, 2023.
- [2] Takuya Akiba, Shotaro Sano, Toshihiko Yanase, Takeru Ohta, and Masanori Koyama. Optuna: A next-generation hyperparameter optimization framework. *Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining*, 2019.
- [3] G. Sekhar Babu, V. Ramya, K. Charishma Sai Lakshmi, M. P. V. Sai Kumar Reddy, G. Bala Nagendra, and R. V. V. Satyanarayana Murthy. Food recommender-system using machine learning and graph clustering. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 2023.
- [4] Jon Nicolas Bondevik, Kwabena Ebo Bennin, Önder Babur, and Carsten Ersch. A systematic review on food recommender systems. *Expert Syst. Appl.*, 238:122166, 2023.
- [5] Paul A S Breslin. An evolutionary perspective on food and human taste. *Curr Biol*, 23(9):R409–R418, 2013.
- [6] Stanford CS224N, Andrew Cheng, and Swathi Ganjaraju. Fine-tuning bert for sentiment analysis, paraphrase detection and semantic text similarity nlp tasks. 2023.
- [7] Jacob Devlin, Ming-Wei Chang, Kenton Lee, and Kristina Toutanova. Bert: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. In *North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 2019.
- [8] Audrey Eertmans, Frank Baeyens, and Omer Van den Bergh. Food likes and their relative importance in human eating behavior: review and preliminary suggestions for health promotion. *Health education research*, 16 4:443–56, 2001.
- [9] Tianyu Gao, Xingcheng Yao, and Danqi Chen. SimCSE: Simple contrastive learning of sentence embeddings. In Marie-Francine Moens, Xuanjing Huang, Lucia Specia, and Scott Wen-tau Yih, editors, *Proceedings of the 2021 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, pages 6894–6910, Online and Punta Cana, Dominican Republic, November 2021. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [10] Giri Gandu Hallur, Sandeep Prabhu, and Avinash Aslekar. Entertainment in era of ai, big data iot. chapter Chapter 5, pages 87–109. Springer, 2021.
- [11] Edward J. Hu, Yelong Shen, Phillip Wallis, Zeyuan Allen-Zhu, Yuanzhi Li, Shean Wang, Lu Wang, and

- Weizhu Chen. Lora: Low-rank adaptation of large language models, 2021.
- [12] Xinwei Ju, Frank Po Wen Lo, Jianing Qiu, Peilun Shi, Jiachuan Peng, and Benny Lo. Menuai: Restaurant food recommendation system via a transformer-based deep learning model, 2022.
- [13] Ashwini Kumar. Recipe recommendation - bert sentence embedding.
- [14] Zhenfeng Lei, Anwar ul Haq, Adnan Zeb, Md Suza-uddola, and Defu Zhang. Is the suggested food your desired?: Multi-modal recipe recommendation with demand-based knowledge graph. *Expert Syst. Appl.*, 186:115708, 2021.
- [15] Chen Li, Yixiao Ge, Jiayong Mao, Dian Li, and Ying Shan. Taggpt: Large language models are zero-shot multimodal taggers. *ArXiv*, abs/2304.03022, 2023.
- [16] Jiazheng Li, Lin Gui, Yuxiang Zhou, David West, Cesare Aloisi, and Yulan He. Distilling chatgpt for explainable automated student answer assessment, 2023.
- [17] Sikai Li, Yilin Jia, and Yuqi Mai. Loracse: Contrastive learning of sentence embeddings using lora. 2024.
- [18] Ying-Chieh Liu, Djeane Debora Onthoni, Sulagna Mohapatra, Denisa Irianti, and Prasan Kumar Sahoo. Deep-learning-assisted multi-dish food recognition application for dietary intake reporting. *Electronics*, 11(10), 2022.
- [19] Yinhan Liu, Myle Ott, Naman Goyal, Jingfei Du, Mandar Joshi, Danqi Chen, Omer Levy, Mike Lewis, Luke Zettlemoyer, and Veselin Stoyanov. Roberta: A robustly optimized bert pretraining approach. *ArXiv*, abs/1907.11692, 2019.
- [20] Hanjia Lyu, Song Jiang, Hanqing Zeng, Yinglong Xia, and Jiebo Luo. Llm-rec: Personalized recommendation via prompting large language models. *ArXiv*, abs/2307.15780, 2023.
- [21] Bodhisattwa Prasad Majumder, Shuyang Li, Jianmo Ni, and Julian McAuley. Generating personalized recipes from historical user preferences. In Kentaro Inui, Jing Jiang, Vincent Ng, and Xiaojun Wan, editors, *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing and the 9th International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing (EMNLP-IJCNLP)*, pages 5976–5982, Hong Kong, China, November 2019. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- [22] Amil Merchant, Elahe Rahimtoroghi, Ellie Pavlick, and Ian Tenney. What happens to bert embeddings during fine-tuning? In *BlackboxNLP Workshop on Analyzing and Interpreting Neural Networks for NLP*, 2020.
- [23] Nils Reimers and Iryna Gurevych. Sentence-bert: Sentence embeddings using siamese bert-networks. In *Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, 2019.
- [24] Mehrdad Rostami, Mourad Oussalah, and Vahid Farrahi. A novel time-aware food recommender-system based on deep learning and graph clustering. *IEEE Access*, 10:52508–52524, 2022.
- [25] Anil Sah and Venkatesh K. Predictive modeling for restaurant menu customization: An fp-growth algorithm-based solution. pages 1–6, 02 2024.
- [26] Amaia Salvador, Nicholas Hynes, Yusuf Aytar, Javier Marin, Ferda Ofli, Ingmar Weber, and Antonio Torralba. Learning cross-modal embeddings for cooking recipes and food images. In *2017 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 3068–3076, 2017.
- [27] Victor Sanh, Lysandre Debut, Julien Chaumond, and Thomas Wolf. Distilbert, a distilled version of bert: smaller, faster, cheaper and lighter. *ArXiv*, abs/1910.01108, 2019.
- [28] Yijun Tian, Chuxu Zhang, Ronald Metoyer, and Nitesh V. Chawla. Recipe recommendation with hierarchical graph attention network. *Frontiers in Big Data*, 4, 2022.
- [29] Thi Ngoc Trang Tran, Muesluem Atas, Alexander Felfernig, and Martin Stettinger. An overview of recommender systems in the healthy food domain. *Journal of Intelligent Information Systems*, 50, 06 2018.
- [30] Iulia Turc, Ming-Wei Chang, Kenton Lee, and Kristina Toutanova. Well-read students learn better: On the importance of pre-training compact models. *arXiv: Computation and Language*, 2019.
- [31] Maggie Xiao. Recipe guru, a recipe recommendation web app based on nlp.
- [32] Weiguang Xie, Hongliang Lou, and Muhammad Babar. Implementation of key technologies for a healthy food culture recommendation system using internet of things. *Mob. Inf. Syst.*, 2022, jan 2022.
- [33] Feng Xue, Xiangnan He, Xiang Wang, Jiandong Xu, Kai Liu, and Richang Hong. Deep item-based collaborative filtering for top-n recommendation. *ACM Transactions on Information Systems (TOIS)*, 37:1 – 25, 2018.